

PUBLIC PRIVATE SECTOR WAGE DIFFERENTIALS IN PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT: This study explored the Public-Private sector earning differentials for male and female employees in Pakistan. The study utilized nationally representative Labour Force Survey data (2010-11). The Ordinary Least Square and Oaxaca Blinder wage decomposition methods were used to obtain the robust estimates and decompose the earning gaps into the portion that is explained by the differences in productive endowments and the unexplained part due to unknown factors. The findings reveal that public sector employees have higher wage premium. Furthermore, public-private wage differential is higher for females than for males. Our results also show that the explained part of public-private wage differential for males is larger than explained part for females. Female wages in private sector are low as compare to public sector.

KEYWORDS: Public- Private, Wage differential, Gender, Oaxaca-Blinder, Decomposition

1. INTRODUCTION

In developing countries, public sector has a substantial share in total employment. Therefore, it could affect rest of the labor market and its operations (Hyder & Reilly, 2005). There is segmentation in the Pakistani labor market. Segmentation can result in different groups like men and women, receiving different wages for the same work. Different wage conditions arise from differences in human capital i.e. skills, formal education, experience or structure of wage (Gyimah-Brempong & Fichtenbaum, 1993). Pakistani labor market has wage differential between the workers of public and private sector (Aslam & Kingdon, 2009). To understand the potential pay gap between public and private sectors it is important to understand wage determination. The process of wage determination is different in public and private sectors and one of the main factors of wage differentials. Public sector wage determination policy has an influence on whole economy both at micro & macro level as public sector is dominant employer. The economic literature on public private pay differential presents many theoretical justifications for the fact of wage premiums in public private sector. The basic and plausible explanation is that wage setting in public sector is associated with political constraints but private sector is subjected to profit constraints. For instance, public sector workers are not only busy in production of goods and services but also involved in political activities which results in higher income (Heitmueller, 2004). Wages in private sector are settled according to productivity of employees and in public sector this process is based on other labor market conditions (Gunderson, 1979).

Wage setting in public and private sector may be affected by various possible dimensions such as changing conditions of product market, enforcement to control production prices, latest technologies, political pressure to control government spending and role of unions etc. (Heitmueller, 2004).

There are some public sector features that cause wage differential. (1) Generally employees are more interested to work in public sector because they think public sector jobs are riskless while some are interested to do work in private sector because of freedom of job choice (Naheed, Younas, & Arif, 2012). (2) Low wages in public sector make employees less efficient and less productive which makes their performance very poor. Low wages decrease worker's inducement in public sector and it creates difficulty to recruit efficient and skilled workers which make public sector performance very poor (Leping, 2005). (3) Because of poor administration and inefficient control in public sector, employees of this sector perform irresponsible duties and often remain absent from work (Ali, 1998).

Wage differential might be in favor of private sector but it has a significant effect on public sector and

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its output. Firstly, it results in massive brain drain from public to private sector. Secondly, a big public-private wage gap makes public sector worker less efficient and less virtuous it results in low production. Furthermore, this public private wage gap creates dissatisfaction and anxiety in public sector employees as they demand higher wage. As evidence from 2013, All Pakistan Clerks Association (APCA) has gone on strike for higher wages. Similarly in 2010 teachers of Bahria Foundation School protested for increase in salary. Moreover, in 2012 Young Doctors Association (YDA) protested against the government for paying low income. These are the recent instances that put pressure on employers to increase wage of workers. Thirdly, widening wage gap encourages corruption in public sector.

Therefore, it is worth studying the earning differential of public and private sector workers in Pakistan. As it results in wastage of resources and create social problems.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is to investigate the public-private wage differential in Pakistan. This study intends to achieve following specific objectives,

- i. To decompose the wage gap between public-private sectors into explained and unexplained parts
- ii. To decompose the wage gap between males of public-private sector
- iii. To decompose the wage gap between females of public-private sector
- iv. To give some policy recommendations.

1.2 Organization of Study

Section two presents the review of literature. Section three explains data and methodology while section four presents the results of study. Last section concludes the study and suggests policy options.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Akarçay Gürbüz & Polat, (2016) analyzed the public-private pay gap in Turkey, using Household Labor Force Surveys. This paper used two estimation methods Oaxaca-Blinder (Blinder, 1973; Oaxaca, 1973) decomposition technique and (Chernozhukov, Fernández-Val, & Melly, 2008) decomposition using quantile regressions. The results suggested that there was a positive premium on small income and in the public sector penalty of working at higher end of distribution. Price effect was high while penalty exist.

(Molato, 2015) estimated the wage gap between the workers of public and private sectors in Philippines. The data was taken from merged Labor Force Survey and Family Income Expenditure Survey conducted by National Statistics Office of Philippines for the year 2009. (Molato, 2015) used the linear regression model to compute the wage differential between public-private sector employees. The results showed that public sector workers hourly wage was greater than those who work in private sector. These higher wages were due to pro social activities in public sector employees. However, public sector employees working hours were less relative to private sector workers. Moreover, this paper found that college graduates prefer government jobs. Although, graduates with specialized skills want to work in private sector.

(Antón & de Bustillo, 2015) concentrated on public-private wage differential in Spain. The analysis was based on Wage Structure Survey 2010 data source. Furthermore, to estimate the quantitative proportion of wage differential two methodologies were adopted, the first one was Oaxaca Blinder decomposition and the second one was Quantile Regression. The findings of the study were that public sector workers had positive premium and this premium was defined by explained and unexplained parts. The male and female discrimination was low in public sector while high in private sector. Public sector premium

was low in education, social work and health sectors. The process of public sector downsizing was attributed to wage differential and gender discrimination.

(Daoud & Shanti, 2012) analyzed private and public sector employment choice and wage differential for Palestine. They also examined the wage differential by sector and gender. For practical analysis they used the Labor Force Survey of Palestine Central Bureau of Statistics for the years 1999, 2001, 2007 and 2010. The results show the clear differences by gender for returns to education, employment choice by sector and gender wage differential. The Oaxaca Blinder decomposition shows the gender discrimination is in the favor of females, as female hourly wages are higher than males in public sector. Although, private and public sector results are mixed. Moreover, in private sector education level is low as compared to public sector.

(Voinea & Mihaescu, 2012) revealed the wage inequality in public and private sector in Romania. The employment in public sector offers additional benefits and substantial share of wage premium of about 10%. Study utilized the data from Romanian Household Budget Survey from the period 2004 to 2009. In this study 3000 house hold were taken as sample per month. The Mincerian human capital model is employed. Study indicates that only half premium can be attributed to personal characteristics. Results show that outcome of the self-selection is insignificant. However the premium is still significant and positive after controlling.

(Naheed et al., 2012) investigated the wage difference in private and public institutions and found that in public sector employees are not only highly qualified but also have large wages rather than private sector employees. For empirical analysis study utilized primary data. A questionnaire was established to obtain data and was filled by the workers of private –public educational institutions in Wah Cantt. The sample ages were between 15-60 years. The results showed that individuals working in public sector had greater income and satisfaction levels than private sector employees. However, education has significant impact on wage. The study indicated higher education generate higher income. Moreover, variables like experience, education good environment and skills had greater effect on income level.

(Laušev, 2012) explored the consequence of economic transition on private-public sector wage differential across the income distribution in Hungary economy from 1992 to 2003. The time period covered in the examination of the public sector had observed privatizations at large-scale and restructuring all the way by a quantity of wage reforms. The study discovered that equally male and females in the public sector fared considerably not well than their private sector equivalents through 1990s, however this penalty decreased to approximately zero until 2003. The consequences from quintile regressions established that the public sector wage division was more condensed than in the private sector and therefore employees at and over the middle fared considerably worse off and having a public sector position yet by the end of the phase considered. The results were reinforced through the technique of decomposition of differences in distributions. Furthermore, the study observed public sector wage penalties for different skillful groups of employees. Results demonstrated that the public sector within-group wage equalizing outcome for male graduates in Hungary was three times larger than the parallel estimation reported by research in developed market economies.

(Maczulskij & Pehkonen, 2011) examined public-private sector pay gaps in Finland through quantile regression method. Data was taken from many registers of statistics Finland from 1995-2004. The three steps were used to control three important factors. First, earning function was estimated by using quantile regression method and wage differential vary with earning function. Second, controlled endogeneity in public-private sectors. Third, the possibility of reward on skills may differ between

industries. The results show that men get 3% premium at lower end jobs in public sector. Males wage differential is negative and between 5-10% at median and upper end of distribution. In the public sector women had high wages and premium was greater at upper end of the earning distribution.

(Aminu, 2011) examined the impact of wage review of 1998 in Nigeria and on the differential in disburse for private and public sector employees of the similar age, qualification and education. Empirical investigation based on the model of Mincerian human capital that was carried out for urban male workers only (as they compose an identical group) in the private and public sectors. The consequences achieved showed that earlier than the wage review of 1998, the workers in public sector suffered a pay difficulty of 6.78% whereas about one year later than the review, workers in public sector enjoyed a payment of 35.07%. In private sector the absence of any wage reduction, this result proposed that the accomplishment of the 1998 wage review achieved something in making the public sector employees better salaried than their private sector corresponding workers and it can be concluded that the remuneration raise in the public sector attained its disguised objective of restoring the age-long reduced pay in the sector.

(Yavuz, 2011) examined the public sector in under developed countries probably to influence private sector wage and service decisions and therefore had an effect on the combined labour market. In this study, surplus public service was examined beneath the efficiency salary structure to discover out how effort (productivity) and wage difference among private and public sectors truly influence the labour market or also more particularly equilibrium levels of wages, employment and productivity. These differences were assumed to be as exogenous later on this postulation was relaxed. The study indicated that how the total welfare responds to changes in these differentials in expressions of two different models. The results demonstrated that a struggle of increasing employment through the government finally led to a decrease in overall welfare by shortening private employment. Study contributed to the presented work by giving a different approach via depending an explicit external opportunity, specifically the government sector, to the efficiency wage theory.

(Aslam & Kingdon, 2009) explored the public – private sector wage gap for males and females in Pakistan. The latest nationally representative data (The Pakistan living standard measurement survey) was used. This paper estimated *ceteris paribus* public-private wage gap for males and females. The Oaxaca decomposition technique was used. Results indicated that public sector employees have big wage premium and there existed a large wage gap for females as compared to males. Whereas, wage differential in account to personal characteristics was associated with males, this was not in the case of females.

(Kapsos, 2008) explored the determinants of wage and gender wage gap in Bangladesh. Kapsos adopted Blinder-Oaxaca model and Mincerian model to decompose and measure the wage differentials. The wage differentials can be expressed by the differences in personal and productive factors and the differences due to other unknown factors. The study revealed the first analysis on hourly gender wage gap including the variables establishment size, pay gap by industries and level of schooling and the first quantitative analysis that presents the effects of occupational and industrial wage gap for females and males in Bangladesh. The study also offered gender discrimination wage structure in Bangladesh. The results showed that female earnings are 21% lower than males. Findings showed that schooling was an important factor for decreasing the gender gap, gender gap was higher among non-qualified employees and other big gender gap existed among the employees with primary level of schooling.

(Mukherjee, 2007) investigated the trends in Wage-Differential in India. Inequality in wages was

responsible for socio-economic disparity and may even emphasize them. For achieving the equal development in earnings and wages was hence desirable. Study explored the patterns and trends in wage differential in post-reform period of India by applying the decomposition technique. It evaluates the trends among group disparities across gender, region, and occupational group and job type. It was analyzed that even as vertical differential or disparity between inter-group were coming downward in expressions of wage rate, in terms of entire earnings they were growing, Since other than proportionate increase in disparity in job availability and labor demand. Decomposition analysis demonstrated that wage differential among groups was primarily due to difference in skills. Just a special group plan may help in lowering the gap in wages.

(Chatterji, Mumford, & Smith, 2007) analyzed the importance of personal endowments, workplace characteristics and occupation for earning differences in public and private sector workers. The data for Bratin 2004 was used. The results showed that the sectoral earning differential is different between gender and that earning differential is different between sectors. The public and private pay gap due to the role of workplace features was huge and substantial. The high earning was linked with family friendly policies in public sector for males and females.

(Hyder, 2007) investigated the reactions on the preference for jobs in the public sector between a sample of jobless people in Pakistan to inform on the survival of public sector job lines. Study used cross-sectional data taken from Labour Force Survey (LFS) for Pakistan for 2001-02. The examination covers the entire rural and urban areas of the five provinces of Pakistan as cleared by the 1998 population census. The predictable salary equations were subject to correction based on Lee's (1980) process, and with suitable instrumentation, yield vectors of unbiased earning coefficients for the related sectors. The observed approach permitted job predilection to influence joblessness period. The possible wage gain an unemployed person would take pleasure in a public sector employment was establish to use no self-governing effect on the stated preference showing that fringe advantages and job situations were maybe first and more essential considerations. The public sector stated preference for an employed was found to be connected with higher uncompleted periods. The estimated result recommend that, on average for education and any other characteristics, those jobless who stated a preference for job in public sector had higher unfinished durations of among four and six months. This judgment was taken to verify that there are extensive lines for public sector jobs in Pakistan.

(Richard, 2007) studied the male-female salary determination and gender inequality in Uganda. The research used the countrywide household survey 2002/03 gathered through Uganda bureau of statistics. It was discovered out that male-female wage space was approximately 39%. Wages for equally males and females are predicted by applying Heckman selection model. Model was engaged to correct for selectivity at the phase of entry into the labour market place. Estimations from the salary equations equally for men and women with sector selection and sample highlight the significance of demographic factors, human capital and local labour market segmentation in salary determination. The outcomes from the sex wage gap breakdown by Oaxaca (1973) and Neumark point to bigger wage discrepancy ascribed to discrimination and that the major section of the unexplained salary gap stems from womanly drawbacks. The research suggested policies that decrease gender disparities, mainly those strategies that had an encouraging effect on the empowerment of female who experience discrimination in education and job environment.

(Ramoni-Perazzi & Bellante, 2006) explored the wage differential between public and private sector employees. U.S.CPS data was used for the years 1992-2000. Lee's two step methods were used to compare the pay gap of public and private sector employees. Results showed that federal employees

have wage premium. The employees that were working for private sector were underpaid. The public sector workers were paid lower than private sector employees.

(Anos Casero & Seshan, 2006) examined that public sector employees received pay premium in Djibouti and proceeded to education dissimilarity across the sectors. Public and Private sector wages were estimated by using household survey of 1996, whereas control for selectivity was done by applying Heckman's two stage approach. The study found that public sector of Djiboutian workers received a wage premium, self-governing of their individual characteristics and human capital endowments, and are extra likely to be male and have parents in the public sector. Employees in the public sector made higher private rates of return to schooling than do private sector employees with post-secondary schooling. The outcomes lifted up concerns regarding the present government's hiring and wage situation practices that generate alterations in the labor market and were not competently allocating public and labor resources.

(Hyder & Reilly, 2005) observed the pay gap in public and private sectors of Pakistan by using the data from Labor Force Survey for the years 2001 and 2002. Like many other economies, in Pakistan workers in public sector tend to have both higher education level and income as compared to private sector. Moreover, in Pakistan public sector had more solid distribution of pay and little gender wage gap. The size of the public sector wages was captured by utilizing the sample of pooled data on all workforces. OLS and Oaxaca Blinder methodology were used. Empirical analysis of the study recommended that two-fifth of the raw difference in average pay between public and private sector is due to the difference in individual characteristics. The predictable *ceteris paribus* mark-up of public sector was order of 49%. The regression estimation proposes that when the movement of wage differential moved up, the mark-up turned down monotonically.

(Leping, 2005) measured the wage differential between public and private sector through means of quantile regression method. The results from quantile regression showed that for higher quantiles there was a negative wage gap whereas, there is no remarkable difference in incomes for lower quantiles. The women working in public sector get more benefits than men; the highly qualified workers in public sector earn more than low qualified workers.

(Cheng, 2005) investigated the gender wage gap between the public and private sectors and analyzed the factors that were responsible for changes in wage gap between 1991 and 1996. The two estimation techniques were used for analyzing the Oaxaca decomposition and Juhn-Murphy-Pierce decomposition techniques. The paper estimated and decomposed wage gap into two components i.e. explained and unexplained for government sector and private sector for the census year 1991 and 1996 in Canada. The author examined the changes in wage differential in public-private sectors for the years of 1991 and 1996. The estimation results revealed that there was a pay gap in public sector and private sector, but the wage gap was low for state sector relative to private sector. In 1996, unexplained gap was 67% in the public sector while for private sector it was 76%. However, males' return on personal characteristics was higher than females. The overall gender pay differential tends to be lower during 1991 and 1996 in both sectors, and the reason behind was shrinking of unexplained portion.

(Heitmueller, 2004) examined the public private pay differentials in Scotland. The Bratin household survey was used for analysis. After implementation of endogenous switching model results showed that unadjusted earning gap was 10% for men and 24 % for women. For men this wage differential was because of differences in productive features and for women situation was more doubtful. The findings also revealed that there was a sizeable wage premium for private sector male workers whereas, no sample selection biasedness for women. The sector choice for men was associated with unobservable.

Moreover, analysis suggested that earning differential was an important feature for efficiency of both sectors.

(Özcan, Üçdoğruk, & Özcan, 2003) explained the wage difference according to gender and self-employment in urban areas of Turkey. Data was obtained from household income survey of 1994. Instead of using the entire data, study utilized the data of Istanbul city. Only the workers who were working in agriculture sector and between the ages of 15 to 65 were involved in analysis. Study observed the returns to education and found that self-employment sector gives the highest wages for men. This shows that in self-employment education was highly valued.

(Gong & Van Soest, 2002) examined the mobility of wage differential among both informal and formal sectors in Mexico, using the five quarters panel data obtained from urban employment survey of Mexico. Study utilized a panel data model of random effects. It contains two equations of wages for both sectors and part of multinomial logistic explaining the labor market condition, in which pay is considered as explanatory variable. For model estimation study used the maximum likelihood method. The results showed that wages were increased as education level increased. The probability of public sector employment powerfully increased with the difference in wages. The replicated change probabilities illustrate that for male employees, the choice among informal and formal sector was driven through wage differential and by ignoring heterogeneity, although right state reliance was very small in amount. The non-contribution of women was very common for labor market.

(Christofides & Pashardes, 2002) to account for the double selection problem of choice between, self and paid employment and employment in the public and private sector. Data was collected from the Republic of Cyprus. Probit models and several models of choice in two types of employment (paid/self) and sector (public/private) were estimated. Using a version of the Oaxaca and Ransom (1994) procedure, the wage gap between the public and private sectors was decomposed. Calculations of public-private wage differentials showed an unconditional gap.

(Adamchik & Bedi, 2000) tried to examine wage differentials between workers in the public and the private sectors. Data was collected from Poland. OLS and maximum likelihood method were used for estimation. Results showed that due to earning differentials it will become hard to keep efficient and talented employees in public sector.

(Nasir, 2000) revealed public and private sector wage gap in Pakistan. Human capital approach was used to explore wage determinants. The study used Labour Force Survey 1996-97 to examine wage gap between public and private sector. Results showed that earning of public sector employees was greater than private formal and informal sector workers. Higher incomes were due to personal characteristics while wage structure was not favorable in public sector. The informal sector earnings were lower than public sector and private formal sector.

(Dustmann & Van Soest, 1997) examined the pay structures in the private and public sectors for West Germany. To examine the differences and developments of wage structure into public and private sectors data was taken from German Socio Economic panel for the years 1984-93. In this analysis regression method was used to measure conditional wage gap. The findings showed that in public sector mean wages were greater for men and women while for men conditional wages were greater in private sector and in public sector conditional wages were greater for women.

(Oaxaca, 1973) investigated the level of female discrimination in United States and presented the quantitative analysis of men and women pay gap. The analysis was based on 1967 Survey of Economic Opportunity. Oaxaca decomposition was used for estimation of gender wage gap. The results showed

that a sizeable amount of male female pay gap was accountable for gender discrimination. However, in the absence of discrimination females plan less working hours because of family commitment.

3. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Oaxaca Decomposition Technique

In labor economics (Oaxaca, 1973) and (Blinder, 1973) decomposition methods have been used on a large scale. Applied economists are using Oaxaca Blinder (OB) decomposition as a standard tool for decomposing mean earning differential between two data sets.

Oaxaca decomposition divides mean earning gap into two parts. A part that is described by group differences in productivity characteristics such as experience and education etc., and both groups are treated same called explained portion. The residual part explains that one group gains more favorable treatment on the basis of same characteristics called unexplained portion. The unexplained part is often used as a measure for labor market discrimination but it also sub sums the effects of group differences in unobserved predictor or difference in specification of parameters. First, portion called characteristics effect and the other portion is called coefficient effect.

In this analysis we decompose average earnings differential for the employees of public and private sectors. First, a single earning function is estimated with one dummy variable that indicates sectoral choice. The earning function is as follows.

$$(i) \quad \ln W = \alpha + X\beta + \varepsilon$$

Where, dependent variable $\ln W$ is the log of wages for i^{th} person. X_i is the vector of observed independent characteristics i.e. Education, age, age square and gender etc. is used and a dummy variable which indicates sector of employment. ε is error and β coefficient measure the returns of related factors.

In the next step, we estimate two earning functions for each sector if coefficient of dummy variable for sectoral choice is significantly different from zero.

The separate equations are specified as follows

$$(ii) \quad \ln W_p = \alpha + X\beta + \varepsilon_1$$

$$(iii) \quad \ln W_{pr} = \alpha + X\beta + \varepsilon_2$$

Where $\ln W_p$ and $\ln W_{pr}$ are the log of wages of public and private sector employees respectively. P denotes the public sector while pr represents the private sector. Education, age, age square and gender are the explanatory variables, β 's are the coefficients and ε_1 and ε_2 are error terms for each equation.

In final step we apply Oaxaca decomposition technique to decompose the earning gap into explained and unexplained portions.

The decomposition equation is as follows

$$(iv) \quad \overline{\ln W_p} - \overline{\ln W_{pr}} = \left[\hat{\beta}_p (\bar{X}_p - \bar{X}_{pr}) + \bar{X}_{pr} (\hat{\beta}_p - \hat{\beta}_{pr}) \right]$$

Where, subscripts P and pr represent public and private sectors respectively. \bar{X} is average of explanatory variable in the model and β shows the return of productive endowments.

In this equation left hand side shows the average earning gap i.e. difference in average earnings of public and private sector workers, while the right hand side is the combination of two parts, $\hat{\beta}_p (\bar{X}_p - \bar{X}_{pr})$ this part is due to the differences in average personal characteristics and the other one $\bar{X}_{pr} (\hat{\beta}_p - \hat{\beta}_{pr})$ is due to difference in the returns on productive factors. Former part is called explained, that shows

earning gap due to difference in endowments of public and private workers. The latter part is called unexplained, indicating the earning gap is due to market discrimination. This procedure is using full sample of workers of public and private sector. In addition this procedure is again used to decompose earning gap of males and females working in public and private sector.

3.2 Data Set

This analysis used the data from Nationally Representative Labour Force Survey of Pakistan (LFS) for the years (2010-2011). The full sample consisted of 21550 observations while missing values and unnecessary values are excluded from the sample. 7093 workers are working in public sector and 14457 workers in private sector. The public sector is consisting of federal government, local body government, public enterprise and public limited company. The private sector includes private limited company, cooperative society, individual ownership and partnership. Table 1 shows the variables used in the analysis. $\ln W$ (log of monthly earning in rupees) is the dependent variable. Age is restricted between 15-65 years. Generally, potential experience is estimated as (age-years of complete schooling-5) in the view that schooling starts at the age of 5 years. This is not applicable in Pakistan because most of children's school going age is not 5 years; hence, a large number of our labour force is not highly educated. Due to this reason in the earning function we use age and age square as the proxy for experience and experience square and used various dummy variables for education to reveal different levels of education. No education is the reference category.

Table 1 Description of Variables

Variables	Description
$\ln W$	Log of monthly income in rupees
Age	Age
Age squared	Square of age
No Edu	Dummy equals 1 if individual has completed 0 years of education, 0 otherwise
Below Primary	Dummy equals 1 if individual has completed 1-4 years of education, 0 otherwise
Primary	Dummy equals 1 if individual has completed 5-7 years of education, 0 otherwise
Middle	Dummy equals 1 if individual has completed 8 or 9 years of education, 0 otherwise
Matric	Dummy equals 1 if individual has completed 10 years of education, 0 otherwise
Intermediate	Dummy equals 1 if individual has completed FA/FSC, 0 otherwise
MA	Dummy equals 1 if individual has completed MA, MSC, 0 otherwise

O degrees	Dummy equals 1if individual has obtained a degree in engineering, medicine, computer, agriculture, M.Phil./Ph.D. or other, 0 otherwise
Public	Dummy equals 1if sector is public, 0 otherwise
Gender	Dummy variable, equals 1if individual is male , female = 0

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, results of study are reported using Labour Force Survey data. Table 2 reveals mean values of variables that are used for estimation. These estimates show the significant differences in the characteristics and earnings among all samples. It is observed that public sector employees are considerably earning more than employees working for private sector. Female workers in government jobs have large wage premium than those working for private sector. Similarly in the case of men, in public sector earnings are greater than private sector. The variable age proxy for experience suggests that public sector employees are on average more experienced than private sector employees. Moreover, in males and females sample both genders are experienced and old in public sector. In public sector Importance of higher education is more such as matric to other degrees all educational dummies have higher magnitude. Therefore, the male and female employees who work in public sector are highly educated and more proportion of employees in public sector has at least 10 years of education. This is the fact that more highly educated female employees prefer government jobs. However we need further information to explore the earning differentials. Therefore we adopt OLS regression and decomposition technique.

Table 2 Means of Variables

Variables	Full Sample			Male		Female	
		Public	Private	Public	Private	Public	Private
lnW	9.2279	9.6074	9.0417	9.6101	9.0475	9.5875	8.9200
Age	34.5111	38.6630	32.4740	39.0824	32.5425	35.5621	31.0154
Age Square	1324.56	1597.082	1190.860	1629.348	1196.150	1358.506	1078.142
Below Primary	0.0308	.0135	.0392	0.0141	0.0406	0.0095	0.0108
Primary	0.1542	.0740	.1936	0.0813	0.1997	0.0201	0.0633
Middle	0.1297	.0778	.1551	0.0858	0.1597	0.0189	0.0586
Matric	0.1613	.2009	.1419	0.2076	0.1445	0.1515	0.0880
Intermediate	0.0930	.1744	.0531	0.1767	0.0508	0.1574	0.1019
MA	0.0651	.1346	.0309	0.1176	0.0238	0.2604	0.1836

O Degree	0.1172	.2288	.0625	0.2175	0.0551	0.3124	0.2191
Gender	0.9307	.8809	.9552				
Public	0.3291						

Table 3 Earning Function – Full sample

Dependent Variable: lnW	
Variables	Coefficient (S.E)
Constant	8.014 (.032)***
Age	0.028 (.002)***
Age Square	-0.00022 (.0000228)***
Below Primary	0.069 (.019)***
Primary	0.08 (.010)***
Middle	0.108 (.011)***
Matric	0.173 (.010) ***
Intermediate	0.34 (.013) ***
MA	0.894 (.015) ***
O Degree	0.694 (.012) ***
Public	0.259 (.008) ***
Gender	0.240 (.013) ***
$R^2=0.42$	$N=21550$

Note: *, ** and *** denote significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels, respectively. The dependent variable is natural log of monthly earnings. S.E is reported in parentheses. No Edu is the reference category for education.

Table 3 shows the results of OLS estimation of full sample. The results show the coefficients of educational dummies in column 2 are increasing with higher levels of schooling up to matric level. The main concern of our estimation is the Public dummy which is positive and significant indicating that there is a wage premium for public sector workers.

In the next we estimate two separate wage equations for public and private sectors workers to decompose wage gap. Table 4 shows these estimated equations that are used for wage decomposition. It is noted that explanatory power R^2 is higher for public sector workers. Education has positive effects on earning. Returns on education increase with the higher level of education in both public and private sectors. Coefficients of educational dummies are almost different for public and private sectors. It reveals the importance of education in both sectors. Coefficient of gender is greater in private sector compared to public sector. It means that gender pay gap in public sector is smaller than in the private sector. All the variables included in the model are important determinants of earnings. The coefficient of variable age (proxy of experience) is statistically significant but different in magnitude.

The study estimates sectoral earning differential for public sector and private sector workers. The earning differential is decomposed into two portions ‘explained’ due to difference in characteristics and ‘unexplained’ due to labour market discrimination. The differential is decomposed using Oaxaca decomposition technique.

Table 4 Earning Function- Public and Private sectors

Dependent Variable: lnW		
Variables	Public Sector	Private Sector
	Coefficient (S.E)	Coefficient (S.E)
Constant	8.073 (.069)***	7.865 (.000)***
Age	.031 (.004)***	.034 (.021)***
Age Square	- 0.00014 (.000045)***	-0.00034 (.000026)***
Below Primary	.039 (.046)	.061 (.011)**
Primary	.065 (.025)**	.073 (.012)***
Middle	.140 (.024)***	.095 (.012)***
Matric	.333 (.020)***	.099 (.018)***
Intermediate	.503 (.020)***	.217 (.023)***
MA	.914 (.021)***	1.010 (.017)***
O Degree	.772 (.019)***	.691 (.019)***
Gender	.115 (.016)***	.375 (.038)***
R ²	0.418	0.234
N	7093	14457

Note: *, ** and *** denote significance at the 10, 5 and 1% levels, respectively. The dependent variable is natural log of monthly earnings. S.E is reported in parentheses. No Edu is the reference category for education.

Public-Private Wage Decomposition

$$\begin{array}{rclcl}
 \frac{\ln W_p - \ln W_{pr}}{\text{Total}} & = & \frac{\left[\hat{\beta}_p (\bar{X}_p - \bar{X}_{pr}) \right]}{\text{Explained}} & + & \frac{\left[\bar{X}_{pr} (\hat{\beta}_p - \hat{\beta}_{pr}) \right]}{\text{Unexplained}} \\
 9.6074 - 9.0417 & = & 0.40784446 & + & 0.157821258 \\
 0.5657 & & 72\% & & 28\%
 \end{array}$$

The OLS estimates reported in Table 4 for public- private sector employees. Public-private sector average wage differential is 0.5657.

The explained wage differential is 0.4078; this indicates that 72% of overall sectors wage differential is due to productivity related characteristics like education and experience.

The unexplained difference in public and private sector wages is 0.1578, this indicates that 28% of public-private wage differential is due to unobserved factors. In public- private wage differential

explained portion is larger that shows public sector workers have big wage premium due to superior content of human capital and their other characteristics. Workers of public sector earn more because wage related characteristics favor them more than private sector workers. It is noted that human capital factors like experience and education are more returns for public sector.

Now move towards the next objective of study i.e. to decompose the earning gap between males of public and private sectors.

Table 5 Earning Function, Males-Full Sample

Dependent Variable: lnW	
Variables	Coefficient (S.E)
Constant	8.260 (.0303)***
Age	0.0284 (.00174)***
Age Square	-0.000228 (.000023)***
Below Primary	0.0586 (.01878)**
Primary	0.0758 (.01011)***
Middle	0.108 (.0107)***
Matric	0.170 (.0103)***
Intermediate	0.345 (.0129)***
MA	0.934 (.0158)***
O Degree	0.703 (.0123)***
Public	0.238(.0079)***
$R^2=0.42$	$N=20057$

Note: *, ** and *** denote significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels, respectively.

The dependent variable is natural log of monthly earnings. S.E is reported in parentheses. No Edu is the reference category for education.

Table 5 shows estimates of earning function of sample of males. The OLS technique is applied to get the required estimates. All the important earning related factors are included such as age, age square, public and education. Our main concern is the public dummy which is positive and statistically significant shows that there is a wage premium associated with public sector male employees.

Coefficients of educational dummies are increasing with higher education. The variable age which is the proxy of experience is also significant indicates the higher earning's association with higher experience. Next step is to compute the estimates of male employees who worked in public and private sectors.

Table 6 Earning Function, Males-Public and Private Sectors

Dependent Variable: lnW		
	Public	Private
Variables	Coefficient (S.E)	Coefficient (S.E)
(Constant)	8.178 (.072)***	8.234 (.034)***

Age	0.032 (.004)***	0.034 (.002)***
Age Square	-.000 (.000)***	-.000 (.000)***
Below Primary	-0.003 (.048)	0.058 (.020)**
Primary	0.057 (.025)*	0.073 (.011)***
Middle	0.144 (.025)***	0.095 (.012)***
Matric	0.331 (.021)***	0.096 (.012)***
Intermediate	0.502 (.021)***	0.216 (.018)***
MA	0.905 (.023)***	1.127 (.026)***
O Deg	0.760 (.020)***	0.709 (.018)***
R ²	0.43	0.24
N	6248	13809
Note: *, **and *** denote significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels, respectively. The dependent variable is natural log of monthly earnings. S.E is reported in parentheses. No Edu is the reference category for education.		

The coefficients of educational dummies for males are positive and have increasing trend in both public and private sectors. In public sector male workers are highly educated and getting higher returns on education such as middle to other degree returns are large compared to private sector except M.A. The coefficient of MA is of greater magnitude for private sector male employees. Larger magnitude of educational dummies indicates the importance of human capital in public sector. Wages of male workers in public and private sectors are not significantly different, but slightly higher than private sector. R² is high for public sector which suggests the strength of the relationship between variables to predict the earnings of male employees in public sector.

Public-Private Wage Decomposition for Males

$$\begin{array}{rcccl}
 \overline{\ln W_{mp}} - \overline{\ln W_{mpr}} & = & \left[\hat{\beta}_{mp} (\overline{X}_{mp} - \overline{X}_{mpr}) \right] & + & \left[\overline{X}_{mpr} (\hat{\beta}_{mp} - \hat{\beta}_{mpr}) \right] \\
 \hline
 \text{Total} & = & \text{Explained} & + & \text{Unexplained} \\
 9.6101 - 9.0475 & = & 0.4843668 & + & 0.0729187 \\
 0.5626 & & 87\% & & 13\%
 \end{array}$$

The earning differential is decomposed into two portions ‘explained’ due to difference in characteristics and ‘unexplained’ due to labour market discrimination.

For males, the total average difference in log earnings between public and private sector employees is 0.5626. Of this total 0.484 (i.e. 87%) is explained by the differences in the characteristics of individuals and 0.0729 (i.e.13%) of this difference in earnings remains unexplained.

In other words, the relatively higher wages of public sector male employees are not fully explained by education and experience.

This wage differential is in the favor of public sector male employees as they get the higher wages compared to male workers employed in private sector. The large explained portion reveals that high wages of male in public sector employees are because of greater endowments.

Now we move toward the estimation wage differential of female employees who worked in public and private sectors.

Table 7 Earning Function, Females-Full Sample

Dependent Variable: lnW	
Variables	Coefficient (S.E)
Constant	7.999 (.1503)***
Age	0.0178 (.00864)*
Age Square	-0.0000172 (.000114)
Below Primary	0.422 (.1384)**
Primary	0.264 (.07652)***
Middle	0.0975 (.0786)
Matric	0.261 (.0533)***
Intermediate	0.358 (.0529)***
MA	0.803 (0.0475)***
O Degree	0.694 (.0457)***
Public	0.444 (.0304)***
$R^2=0.43$	$N=1493$
Note: *, ** and *** denote significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels, respectively. The dependent variable is natural log of monthly earnings. S.E is reported in parentheses. No Edu is the reference category for education.	

Table 7 shows estimates of full sample earning function for female employees. All the important earning related factors are included such as age, age square, public and education. Our main concern is the public dummy which is positive and statistically significant shows that there is a wage premium associated with public sector female employees. Educational dummies are increasing with higher education. The variable age which is the proxy of experience is also significant and indicates higher earning's association with higher experience.

Table 8 reveals the estimates of OLS earning function of female employees working in public and private sectors. All the coefficients for educational dummies and age are almost positive and significantly different from zero. Table 8 shows the different scenario for female workers. Education dummies have increasing trend in both sectors.

The middle dummy is positive for private sector but negative for female workers in public sector. There may be a reason behind this is that majority women adopt teaching profession and private sector often hires women with middle level schooling. This is not in the case of public sector because of strict policies and females can adopt teaching profession at least after matric level. In public sector female workers are highly qualified as coefficients of matric to other degree have large magnitude than private sector educational coefficients. The returns on primary and middle are higher in private sector. The female workers in public sector earn more due to their personal characteristics i.e. education.. Larger magnitude of educational dummies indicates the importance of human capital in public sector. It is noted that female's returns on educational dummies in public sector employment are higher than in private sector employment. It reveals high female discrimination in private sector. R^2 is also large for

public sector which indicates the strength of the relationship between variables to predict the earnings of male employees in public sector.

Table 8 Earning Function, Females– Public and Private Sector

Dependent Variable: lnW		
	Public	Private
Variables	Coefficient (S.E)	Coefficient (S.E)
Constant	8.162 (.207)***	8.067 (.000)***
Age	0.020 (.011) *	0.025 (.225) *
Age Square	0.000022 (.00014)	-.00019 (.00018)
Below Primary	0.518 (.170) **	0.400 (.104)
Primary	0.207 (.124) **	0.232 (.106) *
Middle	-0.140 (.127)	0.158 (.093)
Matric	0.360 (.071)***	0.223 (.089) **
Inter	0.533 (.072)***	0.187 (.073) *
MA	0.996 (.068) ***	0.628 (.069) ***
O Degree	0.871 (.066) ***	0.537 (.230) ***
R ²	0.37	0.16
N	845	648

Note: *, **and *** denote significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels, respectively.

The dependent variable is natural log of monthly earnings. S.E is reported in parentheses. No Edu is the reference category for education

Public-Private Wage Decomposition-Female

$$\begin{aligned}
 \overline{\ln W}_{fp} - \overline{\ln W}_{fpr} &= \left[\hat{\beta}_{fp} (\overline{X}_{fp} - \overline{X}_{fpr}) \right] + \left[\overline{X}_{fpr} (\hat{\beta}_{fp} - \hat{\beta}_{fpr}) \right] \\
 \text{Total} &= \text{Explained} + \text{Unexplained} \\
 9.5875 - 8.9200 &= 0.3040946 + 0.363385545 \\
 0.6675 &= 46\% + 54\%
 \end{aligned}$$

In the last, female’s pay gap in public and private sectors is measured. The OLS estimates are used to estimate wage differentials. The earning differential is decomposed into two portions ‘explained’ due to difference in characteristics and ‘unexplained’ due to labour market discrimination. The smaller part 46% of this wage gap is explained by difference in characteristics and 54% of the sectoral wage gap is not explained by differences in observed characteristics between women in the two sectors.

In other words we can say unobserved or unmeasured variables are more important for women for pay determination compared to men. Alternatively, the larger unexplained part for women compared to men could be because of a greater extent of discrimination in private sector. Thus we can say public sector employees enjoy lager wage premium compared to private sector workers. The gap in monthly earnings expressed in natural logs between the public-private sector is greater for women i.e. 0.6675

compared to that for men (0.5626).

The difference between the public sector wages for females (9.5875) and males (9.6101) is lesser indicating the less wage discrimination for them (male and female) in public sector.

Our findings are different and divergent compared to other studies. This study has an identity and distinction from other author's findings. (Nasir, 2000) found in his study that there is small public private wage differential 0.05 (compared with our sample 0.57) in favour of public sector. The explained part due to personal characteristics was 0.12 (in our sample 0.41) for public sector employees. Private sector employees have big compensation package than public sector workers. The study revealed that large earning gap was due to superior characteristics of public sector employees rather than higher rewards for both male and female workers. Moreover, this study is not directly comparable with our findings because (Nasir, 2000) did not confine his study to the public and private sectors, he divided private sector further in formal and informal sectors.

Public private total wage differential for men is 0.72 (compare with our sample 0.56) and for women is 1.37 (0.67 in our sample). The explained part is 66% (in our analysis 87%) due the personal characteristics and for women is 40 % (46 % in our sample) (Aslam & Kingdon, 2009).

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

The study analyzed the sectorial earning differentials for public and private sectors workers (males and females) in Pakistan. Wage functions are estimated by using the methodology of Ordinary Least Squares. Oaxaca Blinder Decomposition is used to quantify the earning differentials between public-private sectors for men and women. This earning differential is divided into explained part due to difference in worker's characteristics and unexplained portion due to differences in wage structure or market discrimination. This study used the data from Nationally Representative Labour Force Survey of Pakistan for the years 2010-2011.

The Decomposition results show that public-private worker's explained earning differential is 72% and 28% is unexplained. While public-private earning differential for males explained part is about 87% and 13% is unexplained. Similarly, public-private earning differential for females describes the 46% explained and 54% unexplained portion. The regression estimates indicate that human capital variables are the important determinants of earnings and earning differentials.

The main findings of this study are that public sector earnings are higher than private sector earnings. In the case of female workers, earnings are also higher for them in public sector. Thus, there is earning differential between public sector workers and private sector workers. The public sector employees earn a big wage premium. A number of factors make public sector jobs more preferable than private sector like pension, work hours, health care, holidays and fringe benefits.

The study provides many policy implications that could be helpful in minimizing the earning differentials. The most important thing is to stop the exploitation of employees. Government should take direct steps to minimize the differentials between public-private sector earnings. First, such programs should be started which educate and train the employees. Secondly, some steps should be taken in labour policy to avert casualization in employment. This study provides guidance for policy makers and economic planners for designing future wage policies.

Public sector workers should be compensated according to their characteristics and more productive workers should be given more inducements. These measures are necessary to keep the talented and productive labour force in public sector.

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